

A Quest About Waste: Teachers' Viewpoints on Solid Waste Management

Ruby P. Villas

Abstract. Education played a pivotal role in the success of a solid waste management program because it helped people understand the importance of taking care of our environment. This phenomenological study investigated the perspectives of ten elementary teachers at Magugpo Pilot Imelda Elementary School regarding solid waste management. It explored their lived experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms. The study identified three main themes in the participant's experiences: the importance of proper implementation, nurturing good values, and collective effort. Additionally, two themes focused on teachers' coping strategies, including student participation and adequate education on policy. Furthermore, Insights on solid waste management revealed that consistency drove change, and collaboration was vital. These findings shed light on educators' roles in waste reduction, recycling, and environmental education, offering valuable input for elementary school curriculum development and environmental policy. On the educational landscape, solid waste management in schools was crucial for fostering environmental stewardship among students and staff, instilling sustainable habits from a young age. Schools generate significant waste daily, including paper, food scraps, and packaging materials. By implementing effective waste management practices, schools could reduce their environmental footprint, conserve resources, and teach students valuable lessons about waste reduction, recycling, and responsible consumption.

KEY WORDS

1. solid waste management 2. environment 3. teachers viewpoints

Date Received: July 25, 2024 — Date Reviewed: August 01, 2024 — Date Published: September 2, 2024

1. Introduction

The issue with Solid Waste Management (SWM) has become critical in the discourses of the contemporary world, particularly in light of rapid urbanization and increased waste generation around the globe. Effective implementation of SWM is essential to mitigate the dreadful conditions of our environment. Educational institutions, particularly elementary schools, play a crucial role in promoting sustainable practices and environmental awareness among the young minds of primary students. Elementary teachers impact this educational paradigm significantly because they are the primary agents of knowledge transfer and behavioral modeling. They are usually at the forefront of implementing school-based solid waste management programs, which typically include waste segregation, recycling initiatives, and environmental education. However, these initiatives may face a variety of challenges. Understand-

ing their viewpoints and how they deal with these challenges is critical for creating effective policies and support systems to improve SWM in schools. Bundhoo (2018) assessed the status of SMW in the least-developed countries. It was found that waste collection is low and irregular in these countries, leading people to resort to illegal practices such as burning waste and illegal dumping. In addition, sanitary landfilling is almost nonexistent in these places, with some of the few landfills present severely lacking effective leachate or gas collection systems. These least-developed countries also practice recycling, but the primary approach is to collect recyclables for export. Similarly, solid waste composting is usually limited to small-scale efforts, and biogas plants in these areas are primarily used to process animal manure. In South Africa, environmental problems in waste, specifically in plastic pollution, have become a global concern that affects not just humans but also the flora and fauna, soil, and the functioning of the ecosystem. Dalu et al. (2020) conducted a study to investigate whether issues in plastic pollution are being integrated into the school curriculums in the primary and secondary schools of South Africa. Findings indicate that although issues about waste management, such as plastic pollution, have been integrated into the curriculum, there is still a lack of integration of solid waste management practices for proper littering of wastes such as plastics, and there is a low understanding of the peril on the different habitat types might this problem carry. In Ghana, a research study conducted by Boateng (2023) found that schools in their region have different waste management practice systems. However, there is a ubiquitous challenge facing both rural and urban schools in managing waste, particularly in the issue of inadequate resources for effective waste management. While rural schools face challenges because of the poor attitudes of students toward waste management, urban schools face challenges in terms of poor waste

collection routines. Based on the 2018 data, the waste generated by the Philippines annually has increased to 16.6 million tons, making it the third-largest generator of solid waste per year among Southeast Asian countries (Romero, 2020). This continuous increase in solid waste due to rapid urbanization, increased population, and high-level standards has led to many problems regarding solid waste management. According to Olsen et al. (2020), teachers play a crucial role in nurturing students' skills and knowledge, using education to sustain human life, promote sustainable environmental behavior, and achieve sustainable development. The Philippine government enacted Republic Act (R.A.) 9003, commonly referred to as the Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000. This legislation is the legal foundation for establishing a "systematic, comprehensive, and ecologically sound solid waste management program" to safeguard public health and the environment. R.A. 9003 requires establishing institutional mechanisms and strategies to ensure the effective execution of the solid waste management program throughout the country. Consequently, through formal education, teachers can equip students with the necessary knowledge and a comprehensive understanding of emerging environmental problems (Jafer, 2020). Achieving improved environmental sustainability, especially in waste management, demands teachers with the requisite knowledge, positive attitudes, skills, and innovative approaches (Debrah et al., 2021). In line with this concept, Republic Act 9003 emphasizes the integration of ecological solid waste management and resource conservation and recovery topics into formal and non-formal educational curricula. This is intended to foster environmental awareness and prompt action among the population, as Section 2 of the legislation outlines.

There is vast literature tackling solid waste management in many educational sectors. Most of it is focused on students, their attitudes, and

practices regarding implementing the said program in their schools. However, there is a scarcity of research studies focusing on teachers' viewpoints, the people who educate others to do the right thing. In the locality of Tagum, a city in the province of Davao del Norte, many programs and projects have been implemented to manage and improve the solid waste management system. These projects do not only stop in the local government units, but schools are also encouraged and obliged to help keep the environment clean. All institutions, from elementary to college, are tasked with keeping their surroundings clean and neat. However, numerous problems exist in the implementation of this program. These problems include limited school recycling facilities, lack of proper waste segregation, and single-use plastics. Educators play a significant role in educating students and others to recycle the waste they generate. However, their role does not only stop at educating people; they must also embody and practice what they preach. It is in this gap in research that this study was conceptualized. Specifically, this research study will focus on educators and uncover their viewpoints and coping strategies for their problems in implementing solid waste management. The findings of this study will provide valuable insights into educational management, adding to the current pool of knowledge on solid waste management and the role of educators in creating a clean and sustainable

environment.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This study investigated and understood the attitudes and practices of elementary school teachers regarding the implementation of solid waste management. By offering insights into the viewpoints and behaviors of elementary teachers about solid waste management, the study promoted positive change and sustainability within the educational context. They understood their views and behaviors and aided in creating educational initiatives and regulations that will significantly impact teaching eco-friendly practices to young kids. The primary focus of the data collection was on the attitudes and practices of elementary school teachers regarding the implementation of solid waste management in their schools. The results of this phenomenological study helped us comprehend teachers' behaviors and actions in creating a sustainable environment. The insights collected from this study have the potential to influence educational management strategies and professional development programs and develop policy regulations to incorporate sustainability and waste management education into the curriculum.

1.2. Research Questions—This uncovered and scrutinized the attitudes and practices of elementary school teachers about the implementation of solid waste management. The research was executed to address the following inquiries:

- (1) What are the viewpoints of elementary school teachers towards implementing solid waste management in their schools?
- (2) How do elementary school teachers cope with the challenges of solid waste management?
- (3) What educational management insights can be gathered from the findings of the study that concern solid waste management?

Hence, putting into utmost consideration the cited problem situation indicated in the previous sections and stipulated in the research questions, the researcher was driven by the urgency and necessity to conduct this study. The researcher

desired to put into light and scrutinize the attitudes and practices of elementary school teachers about solid waste management implementation in their schools. The researcher hoped that this study would benefit the identified sectors

of the academe, including educational leaders, school heads, teachers, other stakeholders, and future researchers. Educational leaders. Educational leaders could benefit from this study's findings, as they can access substantial repositories of attitudes and practices that they can use to guide future policy changes in the educational landscape. The school heads. The findings of this study might help the school heads or principals to improve further and enhance the implementation of solid waste management in their respective schools. The teachers. The study could serve as a reference for other teachers regarding the practices they utilized to fully realize and implement solid waste management. Other stakeholders might provide better support and assistance to efficiently and effectively improve the policy's implementation. Future researchers. This would be helpful as an additional contribution to their references for future research in school development and waste management. It can also offer them a substantial contribution to their academic arsenal.

1.3. Review of Significant Literature—

1.3.1. *Viewpoints on the Implementation of Solid Waste Management*—Solid waste management (SWM) involves the collection, transport, disposal, and treatment of waste materials to mitigate environmental and health impacts while supporting economic development (Marello Helwege, 2018). Various studies underscore the need for community education and collective efforts to implement effective SWM practices (Edrogan, 2014; Sarino, 2014; Villanueva, 2013). A key component is Environmental Education (EE), which aims to foster environmentally conscious behaviors among students by equipping them with knowledge about environmental issues and sustainable practices (URT, 2009; Panzo, Góis, Mendes, 2022; Marpa, 2020).

Education plays a crucial role in establishing effective SWM programs. Studies have shown that integrating SWM education into cur-

ricula helps develop positive behaviors towards waste management among students (UNESCO-UNEP, 1994; Kimaryo, 2011). For instance, Cruzada and Benedictus (2022) highlight the inclusion of environmental education in school curricula and collaboration between schools and local administrations as effective measures to improve SWM practices. Similarly, Batara (2022) emphasizes the importance of community engagement and technical support for successful SWM program implementation.

Despite these efforts, challenges persist. Studies note that inadequate policies, poor community participation, and insufficient infrastructure hinder the effective implementation of SWM (Marshall Farahbakhsh, 2013; Ning Cao, 2019). In the Philippines, the increase in waste production, coupled with poor implementation of the Solid Waste Management Act of 2000, has led to ongoing problems (Romero, 2020; Paragoso, 2018). Effective SWM requires robust guidelines, awareness campaigns, and collaboration among all stakeholders.

1.3.2. *Challenges in the Implementation of Solid Waste Management*—Several barriers affect SWM implementation, such as limited resources, poor waste collection routines, and lack of student engagement (Boateng et al., 2023; Debrah, Vidal, Dinis, 2021). For example, the integration of environmental education faces challenges like insufficient teaching resources, large class sizes, and lack of government support (Kimaryo, 2011; Van Petegen et al., 2007). Additionally, schools often struggle to incorporate environmental education effectively due to competing curricular priorities (Prisco Cubillas, 2022).

Research reveals that both urban and rural schools face unique challenges in SWM. Urban schools often have poor waste collection routines due to overwhelmed waste management companies, while rural schools lack partnerships with waste management companies, resulting in inadequate waste management prac-

tices (Adeolu, Enesi, Adeolu, 2014; Ortega-Dela Cruz Nabor Jr., 2022).

To address these challenges, coordinated efforts involving governments, educational institutions, and communities are needed to develop comprehensive SWM programs that include education, policy enforcement, and contingency planning (Esmaeilzadeh et al., 2020; San Juan, 2019). By integrating ecological solid waste management principles into educational curricula and fostering community engagement, stakeholders can work towards more sustainable waste management practices.

1.4. Theoretical Lens—The study’s theoretical underpinning was anchored on the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) and the International Solid Waste Association’s (ISWA) Integrated Solid Waste Management Framework (ISWM) (2000). ISWM is a solid waste management planning framework that posits that an effective ISWM system examines how to reduce, recycle, and manage solid waste to protect human and environmental health. Furthermore, it uses local demands and conditions to identify and combine the most appropriate waste management strategies. The major ISWM operations include waste prevention, recycling and composting, and landfill design, construction, and management. As applied in the study’s context, the ISWM theory highlights how solid waste management can be efficiently and effectively implemented. Solid waste management has become one of the world’s greatest development challenges. Schools are among the significant garbage generators in any city or country. Thus, more comprehensive solid waste management solutions within development processes are

required. Meanwhile, Hopkins’ School Improvement Theory (2001) further reinforced the study. The theory rests on two basic assumptions and principles: schools are perceived as centers of systematic change that focus on their internal conditions, and the roles of all school members should be defined so that the school’s missions can be accomplished more systematically and organized. RA 9003 (Republic Act 9003), also known as the Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000, establishes a legal framework for managing solid waste in the Philippines. Local governments must implement comprehensive waste management programs that include source separation, recycling, composting, and proper disposal. Integrating RA 9003 into the theoretical framework emphasizes aligning local waste management practices with national legislation to achieve sustainable waste management objectives. In the context of the present study, waste disposal has been a problem for a long time, yet it still goes unaddressed and unresolved. Hence, Hopkin’s theory encapsulated the importance of school improvement, especially its internal conditions. This means that the problem with waste disposal should be addressed and the attitude and practices of teachers should be brought to light. Moreover, it emphasized that it is far from being a one-man job and that everyone in the academe should take part. To sum up, the Integrated Solid Waste Management Framework and the School Improvement Theory capture the focus of the study. The two theories are deemed fitting in analyzing and scrutinizing the attitude and practices of elementary school teachers towards implementing solid waste management in their schools.

2. Methodology

This chapter effectively addresses the study’s objectives by outlining the systematic procedures and methodologies used in phenomenological research. It also explains the selected research design and my roles as the researcher throughout the study’s implementation. Moreover, it offers

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

thorough insights into the research subjects, clarifying their procedures and selection standards.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—A study’s philosophical and qualitative presumptions are vital in steering the investigation. Four fundamental assumptions—ontological, epistemological, axiological, and methodological—form the bedrock for comprehending qualitative research. These assumptions establish the groundwork for the research design and inform the researcher’s approach to the study. A paradigm is as a broad framework or perspective that guides and shapes how researchers approach their studies, formulate research questions, gather data, analyze findings, and interpret results. It encompasses a set of beliefs, assumptions, methodologies, and theoretical foundations that influence how researchers conceptualize and conduct their research (Zukauskas et al., 2018). In this research, the paradigm guided the choice of methodology, methods, and techniques, shaping the overall research process and ensuring coherence in the study. *Ontology.* This study section focused on the relationship between the problem and reality. According to Creswell and Poth (2018), ontology can be defined as the study of the nature of reality. The authors also asserted that the research participants’ perceptions of reality are varied and subjective. This study recognized the complexity and diversity of the realities elementary school teachers face regarding their viewpoints on solid waste management practices in

their schools. Every participant’s story added to a diverse yet collective understanding of their experiences. My sole responsibility was to use theme analysis to capture these various realities and provide a thorough picture of the experiences, perspectives, challenges, and coping strategies teachers encounter in implementing solid waste management. *Epistemology.* Epistemology deals with the nature of knowledge and the relationship between the knower and the known. According to Creswell and Poth (2018), the researcher should try to reduce the gap between them and the participants based on the epistemological premise. By engaging directly with the participants, I became an “insider,” facilitating a more authentic and nuanced data collection. This approach supported gathering firsthand experiences, perspectives, and insights, which were critical in exploring the participants’ subjective realities. *Axiology.* It concerns the influence and importance of my values as a researcher in this study. According to Creswell and Poth (2018), acknowledging and openly discussing the researcher’s values that shape the study was crucial. The values which influence how data are interpreted and presented are explicitly acknowledged in the research process. As a researcher, I handled each participant’s narrative with care and integrity and always had the utmost respect for the information they provided. This commitment guaranteed that the

experiences and viewpoints of the participants were communicated truthfully, mirroring their individual and research values. **Methodology.** According to Crotty (2020), this is "the strategy, plan of action, process, or design lying behind the choice and use of particular methods and linking the choice and use of the methods to the desired outcomes." Its objectives are to explain, assess, and defend procedures. This study explored the viewpoints of elementary school teachers and their experiences, coping strategies, and insights into the implementation of solid waste management using a qualitative methodology. In order to support the ontological and epistemological tenets, techniques like focus groups and interviews were employed, enabling a thorough and sympathetic examination of participants' stories. These techniques were chosen because they can successfully convey the complexity and depth of the participants' experiences. **Rhetoric.** In research, rhetoric was defined as the skillful and convincing use of language, communication strategies, and presentation tactics to effectively communicate concepts, claims, and conclusions to sway the audience's opinion and comprehension of the study (Beqiri, 2018). I utilized an engaging and respectful narrative style that honors the participants' voices while effectively communicating the significance of the findings. This method made the research more manageable and guaranteed that the interpretations were strong and based on the participants' experiences.

2.2. Qualitative Assumptions—Using a phenomenological research methodology, I explore the viewpoints of elementary school teachers regarding their experiences, coping strategies to challenges, and insights on the implementation of solid waste management. I gathered information about their experiences, challenges, and coping strategies about the phenomenon I was studying. Utilizing phenomenology as my guiding qualitative framework, I uncovered the essence and significance of the roles

played by these individuals, emphasizing their unique viewpoints and the intricate details of their experiences. As the study's qualitative researcher, I supported a level of investigation beyond cursory observations. My research aims to investigate participants' experiences, challenges, and coping strategies about the phenomenon. I emphasized the significance of understanding the complexities of the human experience in light of the various perspectives shaped by unique contexts, backgrounds, and personal histories (Neubauer et al., 2019). To capture the profound and complex nature of the implementation of solid waste management among elementary school teachers, my study strongly emphasized in-depth interviews, reflective dialogues, and the analysis of participants' narratives. I hoped to contribute a thorough and contextually rich understanding of the experiences, challenges, coping mechanisms, and insights related to the implementation of solid waste management, all while upholding phenomenological principles.

2.3. Design and Procedure—Determining the precise approach used in a study was crucial to customize the best research design, data collection strategy, and data analysis approach to the study's objectives. I was using a qualitative research design in this investigation. Hammerley (2013), cited in Aspers and Corte (2019), stated that verbal rather than statistical analysis studies are appropriate for qualitative research. The qualitative design was the most appropriate since I studied elementary school teachers' lived experiences, coping strategies, and insights regarding their solid waste management practices in their schools. This meant that I described and elaborated on this phenomenon rather than establishing or refuting theories. However, qualitative research uses specialized methods, including grounded theory, narrative, case studies, phenomenology, and ethnography. Using a qualitative phenomenological research design, I explored the viewpoints and lived experiences

of the participants in this particular setting. I selected this approach because, according to Asper's (2009) cited in Aspers and Corte's (2019) work, the scientific side of phenomenological research focuses on communicating the subjects' viewpoints and the importance of their experiences, then applying scientific concepts to analyze these perspectives. Furthermore, according to Creswell (2018), a phenomenological study is a method of inquiry that describes the participants' complex and collective experiences concerning a particular phenomenon. A key idea in phenomenology was to reduce one's interpretations of a particular phenomenon to a description that could be applied to all situations. Therefore, I identified a phenomenon that revolved around the participants' viewpoints and experiences regarding solid waste management. I then collected information from people with direct experience with this phenomenon to create detailed and accurate descriptions.

2.4. Research Participants—Qualitative analyses typically require a smaller sample size than quantitative analyses. Qualitative sample sizes should be large enough to obtain feedback for most perceptions. Obtaining most or all the perceptions leads to the attainment of saturation. Saturation occurs when more participants are added to the study, which does not result in additional perspectives or information. Glaser and Strauss (2017), as cited in Hennink and Kaiser (2022), recommend the concept of saturation for achieving an appropriate sample size in qualitative studies. For phenomenological studies, Creswell (1998) recommends 5 to twenty-five, and Morse (1994) suggests at least 6. According to Subedi (2021), larger samples in qualitative studies hinder an in-depth exploration of the study phenomenon. There are no specific rules when determining the appropriate sample size in qualitative research. Qualitative sample size may best be determined by the time allotted, resources available, and study objectives (Patton, 2002, as cited in Mullet, 2018).

This study's participants consisted of 10 elementary school teachers at Magugpo Pilot Imelda Elementary School in Tagum City. Five were selected for the In-Depth Interview, and another five were selected for the Focus Group Discussion. These participants were selected based on specific criteria: they had to teach for at least five years and practice proper solid waste management. They are willing to participate in this study regarding solid waste management. I utilized purposive sampling design and judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The participants were chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study (Creswell, 2018). The selection of the participants was purposefully done to ensure that the findings would be authentic (Marshall, 1996, as cited in Vasileiou et al., 2018).

2.5. Ethical Considerations—Ethical considerations are crucial because they relate to the moral principles and guidelines that govern my conduct as a researcher. These principles ensure that I carry out my investigations responsibly, treating participants respectfully and striving to generate reliable and precise information. I adhered to established ethical standards in my research practices to protect participants, maintain scientific integrity, and foster trust within the research community (Resnik, 2020). Social value. This concerns the potential benefits and favorable outcomes that research can bring to society, like addressing problems or improving people's quality of life. I evaluated the societal value of my study by acknowledging its potential impact and importance for the larger community. This ensured that resources are directed toward research that has the potential to create significant advantages for society. Informed Consent. This involved obtaining a participant's voluntary agreement to participate in a research study after they have been provided with sufficient information about the study's purpose, methods, potential drawbacks, and benefits. In this research, I was responsible for ensuring that

the participants fully understood the study and their rights. This explanation allowed them to make an informed decision about participation, thereby preserving the participants' autonomy and dignity. Vulnerability. The vulnerability of research participants pertains to their increased risk of experiencing harm, exploitation, or coercion due to factors such as age, cognitive ability, or socioeconomic status. As a researcher, I needed to acknowledge and consider the potential vulnerability of these participants and take appropriate measures to protect them. This involved providing additional safeguards and support, such as obtaining informed consent from them, ensuring confidentiality, and carefully explaining their rights and the study's procedures in a way they could understand. Additionally, I modified research methods to minimize potential adverse effects, ensuring that the well-being of these participants was prioritized throughout the study. Risks, benefits, and safety. In research, it was essential to carefully evaluate the potential risks and benefits associated with participation in a study and implement measures that safeguard the well-being of participants. These elements involve assessing the potential disadvantages and advantages of participating in a study, along with establishing strategies to ensure the welfare of participants. In this investigation, as the researcher, I meticulously assessed and balanced these factors, ensuring that the potential benefits outweigh the risks. I put adequate precautions in place to minimize harm while optimizing participants' safety, particularly considering student participants' vulnerabilities. This comprehensive approach was crucial to maintaining ethical standards and protecting the participants throughout the research process. Privacy and confidentiality. Privacy and confidentiality in research are about safeguarding participants' personal information and ensuring their identity remains confidential unless they explicitly consent to disclosure. In the context of this study, I was responsible for implementing appropriate protocols to secure participants' data and maintain confidentiality. This includes anonymizing data, securely storing information, and limiting access to authorized personnel only. These measures are crucial to protect the participants' privacy and uphold the research process's integrity. Justice. This concept relates to the equitable allocation of the advantages and disadvantages resulting from research across various segments of society. In this study, I ensured that my research was inclusive, avoiding the exploitation or exclusion of vulnerable groups. Additionally, I strived to make the research's benefits accessible to all who could benefit from them. This approach promoted fairness and equity throughout the research process, ensuring that no group bears an undue burden or is left out of the potential gains from the findings. Transparency. Transparency in research encompasses maintaining integrity at every phase of the study, from its conception and execution to reporting results. In this study, I offered clear and truthful information regarding my research methodologies and outcomes. Furthermore, I was receptive to examination and feedback. Transparency catalyzes trust, credibility, and accountability within the research community and the general public. This commitment to openness ensured that the process and results of my research were accessible and understandable to all stakeholders involved. The adequacy of facilities. This addressed the presence and suitability of the essential resources, tools, and infrastructure required to execute a study efficiently and securely. In this research, I guaranteed access to appropriate investigation facilities. This access facilitated the creation of credible and consistent findings and mitigated potential risks to study participants. The proper facilities ensured that the data collection and analysis were conducted under conditions that upheld the highest research integrity and safety standards. Community involvement. This encompasses the dynamic involvement and active

engagement of community members, stakeholders, or the intended study population throughout the research journey, from initial planning to sharing research outcomes. In this study, I engaged the community to guarantee the study's relevance, acceptability, and potential impact. Additionally, this involvement fostered trust and cooperation between me and the community. Engaging with the community not only helped to tailor the research to be more effective and meaningful but also enhanced the overall quality and applicability of the results. Plagiarism and fabrication. Researchers should strictly follow principles of academic honesty and integrity. This entailed giving proper credit to the work of others, presenting original contributions, and verifying the accuracy and authenticity of data. In this study, I employed tools like plagiarism detectors. I maintained thorough documentation of my research procedures to ensure that my work was devoid of plagiarism and that all data and discoveries were authentic and reliable. By upholding these principles, I enhanced the credibility and trustworthiness of the research community.

2.6. Data Collection—This study employed a systematic data collection procedure. Several steps were taken to adhere to the proper data collection procedure, ensuring the data collection's accuracy and objectivity. The following is the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed. I was securing endorsement from the Dean of Graduate School, the Schools Division Superintendent, and the School Principal. To initiate the data collection process, I secured endorsements from key stakeholders, including the Dean of the Graduate School, the Schools Division Superintendent, the School Principal, and the participants' parents. This process involved submitting formal letters outlining the research objectives and methodology, accompanied by any supporting documents. This crucial step took place within the third week of October 2023, ensuring that all necessary permissions

were in place before proceeding with the collection of data. This proactive approach not only facilitated compliance with ethical standards but also fostered a cooperative environment among all parties involved. Asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. Upon receiving the endorsement, I requested permission from the school's division superintendent. This required submitting a formal letter detailing the research proposal's significance to the educational community. Along with the letter, I attached Chapters 1 and 2 of my dissertation and the research instrument, clearly explaining the study's objectives and participant identification process. Moreover, I waited for the response from the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS) before proceeding with the data collection. This step took place during the last week of October 2023, ensuring that all necessary approvals were in place to conduct the research ethically and effectively. Asking for permission from the school heads. Once permission was granted, I sought approval from the school heads of the selected institutions. This step involved submitting formal request letters to each school head, outlining the research's purpose and the expected data collection timeframe. I asked for permission to conduct the study from the first week of November 2023. Obtaining consent from the participants. With the school heads' approval, I asked for consent from the research participants through informed consent forms. These forms clearly explain the research purpose, participant rights, and confidentiality measures. This process ensured that the participants were fully informed and agreed to participate. Asking for consent from the participants was done last November 2023, in the second week. Conducting key informant. Upon securing consent from all participants, I scheduled and conducted the interviews using a structured or semi-structured interview guide to ensure consistency and reliability in data collection. The interviews took place the same week

after obtaining the informed consent. Transcribing the interviewees' responses. Following the interview sessions, I meticulously transcribed the interviewees' remarks, diligently taking account of non-verbal cues and contextually relevant details. This procedure used audio recordings and field notes to comprehensively capture the breadth of participants' reactions. The transcription of interviewee responses was done in the third week of November 2023.

2.7. Data Analysis—After collecting the data, I embarked on data coding and thematic content analysis. This involved methodically structuring the transcribed data into categories, subcategories, and themes from the interview dialogues. By discerning patterns and connections within the data, I formulated conclusions and gleaned insights directly related to the research objectives. This process allowed me to interpret the data effectively, ensuring that the findings accurately reflect the experiences and perspectives of the participants. In this study, I employed Creswell's Thematic Analysis approach, which was particularly suited for encompassing a range of perspectives and portrayals in participants' feedback. Adopting thematic analysis authenticated the portrayal of individual components and facilitated the categorization of identified patterns within the provided responses. Thematic analysis is a qualitative research technique used to recognize, scrutinize, and interpret patterns or themes present within qualitative data in textual, visual, or other formats. As a qualitative research approach, the thematic analysis allowed researchers to systematically arrange and dissect complex data sets. It involved searching for overarching themes that encapsulated the narratives embedded within the data. This process necessitated the identification of themes through meticulous examination and repeated review of transcribed data (Dawadi, 2020). This methodical approach helps ensure that the analysis was both comprehensive and reflective of the data collected,

providing deep insights into the study's objectives. Therefore, I used Creswell's Thematic Analysis in my research, which necessitated extensive theming and transcript interpretation. According to Caulfield (2020), there are multiple essential phases in Creswell's Thematic Analysis, including familiarization, coding, generating themes, reviewing themes, defining and labeling themes, and writing up. I became fully immersed in the intricacies and subtleties of the content as I became acquainted with the data to begin this process. After that, I started categorizing the data using semantic richness to group different informational components. I created themes that encapsulated the main ideas of the data using these codes. After that, these themes were examined and improved upon to make sure they appropriately depict the dataset. Every theme had a definition and name that elucidates the fundamental ideas. The last step entailed combining the themes and insights into a cohesive article that clearly conveyed the study's conclusions. This methodical approach guaranteed a comprehensive examination and enhanced the comprehension of the information.

2.8. Analytical Framework—The analytical framework in phenomenological research was a methodical and structured approach to data analysis, interpretation, and presentation. In this research study, I used Colaizzi's method to analyze data from the interviews and discussions with the participants regarding their viewpoints and lived experiences in implementing solid waste management. According to Morrow et al. (2021), Colaizzi's (1978) method features a distinctive seven-step process offering rigorous analysis, closely adhering to the data at each stage. This method culminated in a concise yet comprehensive description of the phenomenon under study, which was validated by the participants who experienced it. The effectiveness of this approach relies on rich first-person accounts of experiences, which can be collected through various means. Although face-to-face

interviews are common, data can also be gathered from written narratives, blogs, research diaries, online interviews, and other forms. This method enabled researchers to uncover emergent themes and explore the intricate relationships between them (Wirihana et al., 2018).

Data Familiarization. By reading and rereading the transcripts several times, I fully understood the meanings conveyed by the participants and gained a global sense of the phenomenon being studied. This thorough review process is crucial for fully grasping the nuances of participants' statements, enabling a deeper analysis of their experiences.

Identifying Significant Statements. I carefully identified every statement in the narratives that was directly related to the phenomenon I was studying. In order to identify and highlight phrases and descriptions that shed light on the particular experiences under study, a thorough examination of the gathered data—such as written narratives or transcripts of interviews—must be conducted. This step was essential to ensuring that my analysis stayed on topic and provided a strong basis for future thematic development.

Formulating Meanings. After carefully examining the important statements, I determined meanings that were pertinent to the phenomenon. Although Colaizzi admits that complete bracketing is never possible, I reflexively bracketed my presuppositions to stick closely to the phenomenon as experienced. To guarantee that the analysis stays rooted in the participants' actual experiences, this process entailed putting aside my interpretations as much as was practical.

Clustering Themes. By grouping the identified meanings into themes shared by all accounts, I ensured a rigorous analysis that remained true to the par-

ticipants' experiences. Throughout this process, presuppositions must be bracketed, especially to avoid any possible influence from existing theories. Letting the themes naturally arise from the data rather than being influenced by outside forces preserved the integrity of the analysis.

Developing an exhaustive description. I incorporated every theme generated in the previous step into a comprehensive and all-encompassing description of the phenomenon that I wrote. By identifying common themes from the participant accounts, this thorough description seeks to convey the essence and complexity of the phenomenon. By taking this step, it was ensured that the final representation presents a comprehensive perspective of each participant's experiences.

Producing the fundamental structure. I broke down the lengthy explanation into a succinct statement that highlights the key elements that I believed were crucial to understanding the phenomenon's structure. This succinct synthesis effectively and concisely communicated the essence of the participants' experiences, concentrating on the essential components necessary for comprehending the phenomenon.

Seeking verification of the fundamental structure. I asked participants if the fundamental structure statement accurately reflected their experience by returning it to all participants. I then went back and changed the earlier stages of the analysis in light of their comments. Through this iterative process, the validity and credibility of the findings increased, and the analysis remained firmly based on the participants' perspectives.

The following Figure 2 illustrates this rigorous process, highlighting each step to explain the actions taken to comprehensively analyze the data comprehensively.

2.9. Trustworthiness of the Study—The trustworthiness of a study is about how reliable, sensible, and authentic the research results are, ensuring that the conclusions are trustwor-

thy and accurate. In qualitative research, factors like credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability are often used to evaluate how reliable the study is. These considera-

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

tions were further described below, according to Guba (1981). Credibility. Building credibility entails proving that the results are accurate. Credibility is important for this study because it evaluates whether the results accurately represent the realities and experiences of elementary school teachers who practice solid waste management. I conversed with the participants for a long time in order to gain a thorough understanding of their experiences and to increase my credibility. I also used triangulation, gathering information from a variety of sources, including observations, interviews, and maybe questionnaires. In order to confirm the interpretations, I gave the participants a preliminary version of the findings as part of member checking. Transferability. The degree to which the results of this study can be used in different situations or with different populations is referred to as transferability. While the particular insights were closely linked to elementary teachers' experiences in the implementation of solid waste management in a specific educational environment, I gave thorough explanations of the research

context and methodology. The study's transferability is increased because this thorough, rich narrative enables others, including educators, school administrators, and researchers, to assess how well the results apply to comparable contexts or populations. Confirmability. Confirmability deals with the study's objectivity by making sure that the respondents, not my personal prejudices or biases, shaped the findings. I kept a thorough audit trail that detailed every step of the research process, from data collection to data analysis decisions, in order to ensure confirmability. This methodological transparency made it possible for other researchers to evaluate the research's objectivity by following the study's development and going over the choices made. Dependability. Dependability means proving that the study results are reliable and repeatable in similar situations. This study's dependability was attained through meticulous documentation of the entire research procedure, including the methods used for data collection and analysis. By ensuring that other researchers can duplicate the study and possibly produce

consistent results, such documentation validates the research's dependability. By following these standards, the research not only offered valid and trustworthy conclusions regarding the implementation of solid waste management but also a framework that researchers and other ed-

ucators can use to compare similar learning environments. This methodology enhanced the study's standing in the academic community and provided insightful information for upcoming studies and instructional design.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the analysis of the gathered data from the interview, including the themes and a comprehensive discussion that answers the study's objectives. The themes that emerged from the gathered data were discussed in this chapter. The results present the description and background of the participants along with their assigned pseudonyms to hide their identities.

3.1. Viewpoints of Elementary School Teachers Towards the Implementation of Solid Waste Management In Their School—Education is the foundation of any successful solid waste management program, playing a diverse role in ensuring its efficacy and sustainability. At its core, education develops awareness and fosters a thorough understanding of the crucial relevance of responsible waste management across a wide range of stakeholders. Education encourages people to understand the importance of action and actively participate in waste management programs by instilling information about the environmental, social, and economic consequences of inappropriate garbage disposal. Teachers play an important role in implementing solid waste management strategies in schools. Their responsibilities go beyond standard classroom instruction, including educating, modeling, and actual implementation. Teachers use planned curriculum integration to educate students on the importance of waste management, emphasizing its environmental, health, and sustainability implications. Educators build a strong awareness of responsible waste practices by encouraging discussions, providing hands-on activities, and applying waste management ideas across courses. According to Olsen et al. (2020), educators play a pivotal

role in fostering students' knowledge and skills, thereby supporting the sustainability of human life, promoting environmentally conscious behavior, and advancing sustainable development. Achieving sustainable and efficient waste management in developing nations requires a rigorous focus on enhancing curriculum standards in education and providing teachers with adequate training to impart knowledge and raise awareness among students effectively. There are several reasons why we need to know teachers' viewpoints regarding the implementation of solid waste management. One of them is that they are on the frontlines of waste management efforts within schools. Teachers directly oversee waste disposal practices and interact with students. Their viewpoints provide useful insights into the practical obstacles and prospects of waste management implementation in educational settings. In this study, I interviewed ten elementary school teachers, five from an in-depth interview (IDI) group and five from a focus-group discussion (FGD) group. I explored the teachers' viewpoints and found three recurring ideas clustered into themes. These themes are discussed individually and thoroughly, backed by existing related studies.

3.1.1. Needs Proper Implementation—The health and safety of students, teachers, and

staff are the most important things in school. Any diseases caused by pests like flies and rodents because of inadequate waste disposal pose significant health risks that may harm the people inside the school. Some participants expressed their concerns regarding the implementation of solid waste management in their schools. According to them, the policy needs to be correctly implemented. These responses highlight the challenges of implementing effective solid waste management in schools. While Participant IDI2 expresses initial optimism followed by concern about student behavior in the presence of bins, participant FGD6 emphasizes the challenge posed by the volume of waste generated. Participant FGD10's frustration highlights the ongoing battle to get students to follow waste disposal protocols. Overall, they emphasize the importance of comprehensive strategies and ongoing efforts to promote responsible waste management habits among students. Environmental protection has existed for a long time and is consistently receiving growing interest and attention as having global importance in this era. However, basic waste disposal concepts are still often neglected (Marshall Farahbakhsh, 2013, as cited in Soni et al., 2020). Many people around the globe are aware of the impact of unsuitable waste disposal practices, but the negative implementation attitude creates chaotic situations. Based on the participants' narratives, they are aware of the advantages of this policy because they witnessed how it improved the cleanliness of their school. However, teaching in an elementary school where you deal with many students daily, keeping the school clean and ensuring it is free from any trash lying around the ground is a challenge. With this ongoing problem, they think the policy should be appropriately implemented inside the school because they can still see loopholes in its execution. One participant (FGD10) mentioned that even with trash bins scattered all around the school premises, different trashes of the stu-

dents are still overflowing in the hallways. This finding is similar to Romero's study in 2020, where he found that the 20-year-old Solid Waste Management Act of 2000 was futile due to poor implementation and the lack of households and constituents' participation. The study's result is evidence that despite the efforts of the concerned bodies, everything can still go down the drain if the community does not show cooperation. In this context, some students do not cooperate and do not follow the guidelines for properly disposing of their garbage. Although the positive results are visible and the policy works, the participants still commented that it is insufficient. Managing the cleanliness of the whole school with thousands of students and hundreds of staff might be challenging because not everyone will always follow the rules. According to one participant, some students sometimes forget their responsibilities in keeping their school clean and throw their trash anywhere mindlessly. Paragoso (2018) recommended in his study that to bridge the gap of the lack of basic understanding in waste management, there should be an information drive to be done to educate people on the reasons and purpose of implementing solid waste management. In a parallel study conducted by Kimaryo (2011), as cited in Husamah (2022), it was found that teachers believe that the approach used to integrate environmental education into the curriculum was poorly welcomed and that the information to be taught under environmental education in various areas is not clearly defined. Similarly, the sentiments of the participants in this study are focused on how the policy needs to be properly implemented to achieve a safe and healthy environment for all students, teachers, and staff.

3.1.2. Nurtures Good Values—Engaging children in practical projects targeted at waste reduction, recycling, and correct disposal techniques helps instill a feeling of environmental stewardship. Students who actively participate in these activities obtain a better grasp of their

particular environmental effects as well as vital insights into the global implications of their actions. Students develop a strong feeling of responsibility for the environment via hands-on experiences, which include organizing recycling programs, initiating composting efforts, and lobbying for sustainable practices in their communities. As people see the visible consequences of their actions and learn about interconnected environmental challenges, they become more driven to make informed decisions that benefit the planet's health. The participants mentioned multiple times that the policy keeps the school clean and instills good values in the students by teaching them responsibility. These responses demonstrate the importance of education in shaping students' attitudes toward waste management and environmental stewardship. Participant IDI3 emphasizes values beyond cleanliness, showcasing student-led initiatives like integrating waste management into the curriculum and organizing clean-up drives. Participant M8 emphasizes integrating waste management into lessons to instill responsibility. Participant FGD9 highlights student engagement through initiatives such as color-coded bins. They demonstrate how educational efforts empower students to adopt eco-friendly practices and take responsibility for creating a cleaner, safer environment in their schools. Even though some teachers think that the policy needs more proper implementation, some think it is already great because of its advantages. One is that the policy nurtures good values among the children, instilling a sense of responsibility to care for the environment. One of the participants (IDI3) stated that the student leaders in their school have organized activities and projects, and other students are volunteering to help turn their school into an eco-friendly place. This finding corroborates the study of Gupta, Goel, and Rupa (2019). Their study showed small but noticeable changes when they adopted sustainable practices. These sustain-

able practices by schools in Delhi instilled positive behaviors among students, positioning them as influential 'change makers.' One of the goals of solid waste management in schools is to keep the students safe and healthy. By properly disposing of and managing the waste, the school can keep the school clean and in order, preventing risks, such as the spreading of diseases, from happening. By implementing this policy, the school and teachers can educate the children about the environment. According to Kimaryo (2011), as cited in Husamah (2022), environmental education is critical in helping learners cultivate early-stage understanding, skills, and good attitudes toward the environment. Consequently, environmental education is intended to cultivate environmentally conscious individuals by developing knowledge, skills, concern, and positive attitudes. Equipping the students with enough knowledge about the advantages of this policy will urge them to take part in keeping the environment clean. In a similar study, Panko and Sharma's (2016) case study, as cited in Debrah et al. (2021) illustrated the effectiveness of involving students in hands-on environmental education, specifically focusing on waste management. By actively participating in practical experiences, students not only grasp fundamental principles more profoundly but also cultivate the essential knowledge and attitudes needed for environmental stewardship. By instilling good values to the students and teaching them how to be responsible for their individual trash, we are raising individuals who are environmentally aware of the consequences of their actions.

3.1.3. A Collective Effort—Solid waste management is a collective effort that necessitates the cooperation and participation of various stakeholders within the school community. To properly and effectively implement solid waste management inside the school, the cooperation of students, teachers, administrative staff, and support personnel is required. Each school community member can reduce waste,

recycle it, and dispose of it properly. Students can contribute by adhering to waste segregation rules, participating in recycling initiatives, and increasing awareness about the necessity of waste management. Teachers and administrative personnel can help with these efforts by providing waste management information and guidance, guaranteeing the availability of recycling bins and other facilities, and integrating trash management into the curriculum. Collaborative efforts can result in a healthy and safe environment that benefits everyone. According to Villanueva (2013), as cited in Molina and Catan (2021), all of the methods of waste prevention and management cannot happen in a snap of a finger or through an individual's effort. Instead, it requires collective effort. In the school setting, waste segregation, reduction, and disposal do not solely rely on the cleaning personnel. Managing the waste of the whole school is impossible for the cleaners alone because the school generates tons of garbage and trash. The help of the students, teachers, administrators, and other staff is imperative to keep the school clean. Based on the interview with the participants, they stated that solid waste management is not the responsibility of just one person; it is a team effort where everyone should unite to create a cleaner and greener environment. The participants shared that since the implementation of the policy, everyone has created a clean and safe environment for children where the plants

are brimming with colors and no unwanted trash is littered anywhere. A similar conclusion was drawn in another study conducted by Panzo, Góis, and Mendes (2022). According to them, didactic materials should be developed, and specific steps should be implemented to encourage collaboration between schools and local authorities. This collaborative project aims to improve students' understanding of environmental challenges and the health consequences of poor waste management techniques. Additionally, in the same vein, according to the study of Baula as cited by Punongbayan (2014) as cited in Lualhati (2019), awareness coupled with participation is the key for students to be included and involved in the waste management program of the schools where effective and sustainable implementation of the proper waste management practices could be achieved. The participation of the students in this policy is of the utmost importance because they comprise almost 80 percent of the school's total population. With thousands of students walking around the campus, a little action, such as proper disposal of their trash, contributes significantly to the cleanliness of the whole school. Figure 3 shows the viewpoints of elementary school teachers towards the implementation of solid waste management in their school and the emergence of the three themes: Needs Proper Implementation, Nurtures Good Values, and Collective Effort.

3.2. How Elementary School Teachers Cope with the Challenges in Solid Waste Management—According to McIntosh et al. (2013), as cited in Debrah et al. (2021), the successful integration of sustainability principles into schools and institutions hinges on the dedicated involvement of administrators and teachers. They play a crucial role in championing and embedding these principles throughout the educational system. This requires proactive ef-

forts to promote sustainability initiatives and to incorporate them into various aspects of school operations, curriculum development, and daily practices. By embracing sustainability as a core value and demonstrating its importance through their actions and decisions, administrators and teachers can inspire meaningful change and foster a culture of environmental responsibility within educational settings. Teachers must possess solid knowledge of solid waste

Fig. 3. Viewpoints Of Elementary School Teachers Towards the Implementation of Solid Waste Management in Their School

management (SWM) to address challenges related to waste management and environmental issues, especially in developing nations. As Jafer (2019) highlighted, through formal education, teachers can equip students with the necessary knowledge and comprehension of evolving environmental concerns. Teachers' roles and responsibilities in executing the solid waste management policy are vital as frontline personnel. However, this policy faces various challenges in its implementation inside the school premises. Teachers have an important role and are among the people who need to address and solve these challenges. In this study, I investigated the viewpoints of teachers regarding the implementation of solid waste management in their schools. Along with that, one of my objectives is to delve deeper into the challenges and how teachers cope with them. I interviewed the same ten participants and asked what challenges they encountered in the implementation of solid waste management and how did they cope with it. There are two recurring ideas in the responses of the participants. These two ideas are clustered into themes and are discussed individually and thoroughly and backed up by related literature conducted by different researchers.

3.2.1. Student Cooperation—Elementary students are still kids. They prefer to enjoy playing games with their peers than to clean their

surroundings. That is why encouraging them to cooperate in implementing solid waste management can be challenging for the teachers. Young children frequently have a limited understanding of environmental issues and may not realize the need for their participation in trash management operations. Concepts like the effects of inappropriate trash disposal or the advantages of recycling may be vague and difficult for them to grasp completely. Furthermore, elementary kids have shorter attention spans, making keeping them engaged in waste management activities challenging, especially if they find them boring or uninteresting. During the interview, the elementary school teachers were asked what challenges they encountered in implementing solid waste management. The responses highlight the difficulties of teaching waste management to students. Participants IDI3 and IDI1 highlight the difficulty of maintaining consistency and understanding the importance of recycling, whereas participant FGD7 emphasizes the challenge of instilling personal responsibility for waste reduction. Participant FGD10 emphasizes the significant impact of peer dynamics on student behavior. They emphasize the task's multifaceted nature and the importance of effectively addressing comprehension, consistency, personal responsibility, and peer influence to promote sustainable waste management prac-

tices among students. Thousands of students are studying at the school where the participants teach. The ages of these students range from five to thirteen years old. They still need guidance and someone to follow because some lack the autonomy or authority to take initiative in waste management issues. This finding is similar to Ortega-Dela Cruz and Nabor Jr.'s (2022) study, which investigated grade six students in Laguna, Philippines. Their study revealed that the students had low awareness, knowledge, attitudes, and practices about solid waste management. Despite the school's presentation of solid waste management concepts, a systematic approach with clearly defined goals and procedures is required to emphasize the necessity of trash management. Teachers need to take a stand and initiate the lead to urge the students to cooperate in the implementation of solid waste management. San Juan (2019) stated in his study that community members' participation in solid waste management programs depends on their leader's or officials' actions. Therefore, the participation of the students in the implementation of the policy is highly dependent on the actions performed by the teachers. Suppose the teachers are constantly initiating activities such as proper recycling, segregating, and waste disposal. In that case, the students will mirror their actions, and if regularly done, they will be used to doing it until it becomes a routine and habit. Based on their feedback, they began with small-scale activities to prompt student action, consistently incorporating them into daily routines until students became accustomed to them. One participant (IDI1) described initiating an activity where each student pledged to take a small action to reduce waste and keep the classroom clean. Another participant (IDI3) recounted starting a class project where students had to devise creative ways to reuse everyday items. Participant FGD7 also mentioned implementing a weekly 'Green Day' in their classroom, during which they review waste bins and discuss

progress. Lastly, participant FGD10 addressed the issue of low interest by making classroom waste management a collaborative effort. By making this effort to cope with the challenges of implementing the policy, the participants could advocate for the cleanliness of their environment. They encouraged the students to participate by giving them a sense of responsibility and ownership. Encouraging students to participate and cooperate in policy implementation can struggle when teachers do not practice what they preach. In a comparable study, Adeolu, Enesi, and Adeolu (2014), cited in Albert and Olutayo (2021), also found that in rural schools, the attitude of students is deplorable, and these students lack the basic instinct of appropriating waste in appropriate cans which poses a significant challenge. Children of their age are great imitators; they copy what they see, and teachers should use that to their advantage to encourage student cooperation. Additionally, the teachers can foster environmental awareness among the students by encouraging them to join clubs and activities inside their school. According to Boateng et al. (2023), the formation of environmental education clubs by school authorities among students can be a sine qua non for effective waste management practices among students.

3.2.2. Proper Education on the Policy— Proper education on implementing solid waste management is critical to its success because it provides individuals with the knowledge, skills, and attitudes required to embrace sustainable waste management practices. By educating people about waste management's concepts, practices, context, and importance, we may build a better informed and environmentally responsible society. However, in this study, proper education on the implementation of solid waste management is a challenge for most teachers. These statements highlight the challenges of educating students about solid waste management. Participant IDI2 emphasizes balancing

academic depth with attention spans and curriculum constraints. Participant IDI4 stresses the importance of comprehensive education in light of the difficulty of teaching stubborn young students. Participant FGD6 emphasized the difficulty of ensuring ongoing education within a demanding curriculum. Finally, participant M8 points out the difficulty in making waste management relevant to students' daily lives. They highlight the multifaceted nature of this task, including the need for depth, consistency, and relatability while adhering to time and curriculum constraints. The challenge of implementing environmental education to promote solid waste management has become prevalent in many countries. Studies conducted in various nations have revealed that despite emerging over 30 years ago, the objectives of environmental education have not been fully realized (Barraza et al., 2003, as cited in Bedural, 2018). One of the primary reasons cited is that teachers encounter difficulties in teaching environmental education. One of the reasons is the insufficient knowledge of environmental education principles (Van Petegem et al., 2007), cited in Bourn and Soysal (2021). Based on the participants' narratives, proper education about the policy should be taught to the students early on to help them understand its importance. Children of their age might be stubborn at times, and it is a struggle to help them understand the complexities of environmental education and the essence of solid waste management. The findings of this study corroborate the assertion made by

According to Villanueva (2013), cited in Molina and Catan (2021), education is one of the four critical components of a successful solid waste management program. Based on the interview with the participants, to properly educate their students, they incorporate it into their lessons and create activities to showcase it to the children. Since the students have differ-

Molina and Catan (2021). Their study showed that the students understand the definition of solid waste, the consequences of improper solid waste disposal, prohibited solid waste activities, school initiatives on solid waste, the importance of solid waste management, and students' responsibilities. However, the survey demonstrates that students do not understand numerous regulations regarding solid waste management. To cope with this challenge, the teachers employed several techniques to inculcate the importance of solid waste management to their students. Education is a crucial component of a solid waste management program's effectiveness. People's understanding of the waste problem, its effects on human and environmental health, and the steps they may take to address it can all be improved by educating them and encouraging their participation in waste management programs and initiatives (Chakraborti et al., 2003 cited in Reyes Madrigal, 2020).). The participation of the students is crucial to the success of solid waste management policy. However, no matter how eager they are to cooperate, their efforts will be futile if they lack the proper knowledge. In this context, it is the responsibility of the teachers to properly educate students on the basic concepts of solid waste management. Dealing with elementary students and their young minds, teachers must find a way to teach the complexities of this policy to the students in a manner that they can clearly and easily understand.

ent learning styles, teachers must also keep that in mind when educating the children. Figure 4 shows how elementary school teachers cope with the challenges in solid waste management and the emergence of the three themes: student cooperation and proper education on the policy.

3.3. *Insights Drawn from the Implementation of Solid Waste Management in Schools* —

Fig. 4. How Elementary School Teachers Cope with the Challenges in Solid Waste Management

The viewpoints of the elementary teachers regarding solid waste management are divided. While some perceive it as beneficial since it nurtures good values in the students, some see it as lacking. Also, as a policy, challenges arise every day when implementing solid waste management in schools. As one of the frontline personnel in its execution, teachers have to deal with the challenges and find ways to cope with them to ensure that their implementation is still a success despite the problems and obstacles that arise. In this paper section, I will explore the key themes that surfaced during my interviews with the ten participants. Drawing from their perspectives, encountered obstacles, and the strategies they utilized to implement solid waste management initiatives, I inquired about the educational management insights they could offer, given their substantial knowledge and experience in implementing this policy. During the interview, I gathered two themes. These themes will be discussed thoroughly and individually.

3.3.1. Consistency Drives Change—Ensuring environmental cleanliness entails more than simply disposing of rubbish once and declaring the operation fulfilled. It entails estab-

lishing an attitude of continuous accountability and proactive action. Proper garbage disposal is essential, but it is only one component of a more comprehensive picture of keeping a clean environment. With students attending school five days a week, the accumulation of waste, including single-use plastics, becomes significant due to the sheer number of students contributing to it. This cycle persists throughout the next ten months, from the beginning of classes to the end. Reflecting on the potential volume of waste generated over ten months, the environmental impact is profoundly disheartening. This is why teachers shared that one of the lessons they learned in solid waste management is that consistency drives change.

These statements highlight important lessons learned during waste management education. Participants IDI3 and IDI5 emphasize the importance of consistently setting attainable goals and instilling trust in students. Participant M8 emphasizes the importance of teachers modeling behavior, whereas Participant FGD10 discusses the advantages of incorporating waste reduction into various subjects to promote interconnected learning. They emphasize the importance of consistency, celebration, mod-

eling, and integration in education to promote responsible waste management among students. If each individual is responsible enough to play their part in implementing the policy, they can keep their school campus safe and healthy for everyone. According to UNESCO, environmental education is crucial in enhancing awareness of environmental issues and challenges. By providing individuals with the skills and expertise needed to address these challenges, environmental education fosters attitudes, motivations, and commitments to make informed decisions and take responsible actions toward environmental stewardship (Leicht et al., 2018). Herein lies the responsibility of teachers. As educators, it is incumbent upon them to impart the essential skills, knowledge, and attitudes to students. By consistently reinforcing these lessons, students are reminded of the significance of environmental stewardship. Consequently, they will be motivated to take action and assume responsibility for the environment's well-being. As per the participants' insights, accumulating small but consistent actions has a significant impact. Whether it is the ongoing instruction of basic solid waste management principles to students, the regular reinforcement of their environmental responsibilities, or the continual modeling of desired behaviors by teachers, these consistent efforts collectively shape the students' attitudes and actions towards the environment. The participants believed that consistency drives change. As a result, they recommend to other people, particularly teachers, school administrators, students, and even the local and higher authorities, to consider the long-term advantages of properly implementing solid waste management and how consistency in our actions creates a lot more than creating a clean environment. A parallel study conducted by Agut et al. (2013), as cited in Davis and Davis (2020), emphasized the importance of early environmental education for achieving sustainable living. This necessity arises because children

form their identities during their formative years (Borg Samuelsson, 2022). Thus, instilling environmental awareness and values in children from an early age lays the foundation for sustainable attitudes and behaviors in adulthood. If these positive behaviors are constantly nurtured, the child can grow into an individual who does not only think about their future but also the future of the environment. The participants insistently recommend consistently promoting environmental education, especially among students, recognizing them as the future stewards of our world. By consistently instilling in children the values of environmental responsibility, we can cultivate a sense of duty and accountability within them. Additionally, considering they are still kids, we can start by teaching them the small actions that significantly contribute to the policy's success. When these small actions accumulate, they will create a ripple effect, thereby positively affecting everything.

3.3.2. Collaboration is the Key—To successfully implement solid waste management, people need to collaborate to achieve a common goal. In this context, the goal is to properly execute solid waste management inside the school and keep the surroundings clean and safe so that the students can learn in a safe and conducive environment free from harm and risks, such as diseases caused by pests. Establishing a healthy and safe school environment requires the commitment and cooperation of various stakeholders. This collaborative endeavor includes educators, school administrators, students, parents, and the general public. Working together to achieve this common goal allows each stakeholder to offer their unique perspectives, resources, and expertise to create an environment that promotes the well-being and safety of all participants. During the interview, the participants were asked about the lessons they learned in implementing solid waste management in their schools.

Given the escalating waste crisis affecting

our ecological environment on both local and global scales, there is a pressing need to reinforce solid waste management practices (Choi, 2016), as cited in Saracini and Sidorenko (2019). Furthermore, as highlighted by Sarino (2014), as cited in Lalamonan and Comighud (2020), raising awareness about solid waste management practices can shift perceptions of garbage among individuals. It is crucial to recognize that awareness, when coupled with active participation, serves as the linchpin for community engagement in waste management programs. This synergy enables the effective and sustainable implementation of proper waste management practices, as emphasized by Punongbayan (2014) as cited in Lualhati (2019). When everyone works together to keep the school premises clean, it creates a positive and vibrant community founded on camaraderie and teamwork. According to the participants, collaboration is not a convenience but a necessity. Keeping the environment clean is a shared responsibility, and everyone has a role to play. The success of waste reduction in schools relies on everyone playing their part. That is why the participants also recommended that to improve the implementation of solid waste management further, everyone, from students to teachers, school administrators, cleaning personnel, and even the local and higher authorities, should work together to achieve this goal.

The participants FGD6, FGD9, and FGD14 discussed the importance of collaboration as not a convenience but a necessity. Keeping the environment clean is a shared responsibility, and everyone has a role to play. The success of waste reduction in schools relies on everyone playing their part. That is why the participants also recommended that to improve the implementation of solid waste management further, everyone. Our learners must possess heightened awareness and effectively implement solid waste manage-

ment practices. They are our planet's future stewards and must actively address environmental challenges, which are global concerns. The evident segregation of waste in schools and the community is due to promoting environmental sustainability through educational programs, community initiatives, and supportive policies to reduce environmental impact and promote recycling. As noted by Van Niekerk (2014), as cited in Chatira-Muchopa et al. (2019), they hold significant potential roles as change agents, future guardians of the environment, and managers and developers of ecosystems. Therefore, waste prevention and fostering public participation through comprehensive education and accurate information are crucial factors for the well-being of future generations (Marello Helwege, 2018). Additionally, the role of the teachers here is not just to educate the children but also to oversee the implementation of the policy and ensure that it is going according to the desired outcomes. Furthermore, teachers can connect with the local authorities for further help. According to Ortega-Dela Cruz and Nabor (2022), school authorities must collaborate closely with local government entities to effectively implement efficient solid waste management programs. Such coordination ensures that resources, expertise, and support are appropriately leveraged to address waste management challenges within the school community. Education and awareness programs in schools play a vital role in increasing knowledge about waste management practices, which can help conserve energy and resources, reduce emissions, and safeguard human health. Figure 5 shows the education management insights drawn from the study's findings focused on implementing solid waste management in schools and the emergence of the themes of Consistency Drives Change and Collaboration is the Key.

Fig. 5. Education Management Insights Drawn from the Findings of the Study Focused on the Implementation of Solid Waste Management in Schools

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter presents the study summary. From the summary of the findings, I draw the implications and future directions. The purpose of my study was to find out the viewpoints and coping mechanisms of elementary school teachers. From there, I derived insights about implementing solid waste management in schools. In connection with that, I have utilized a qualitative phenomenological method with thematic analysis to ensure the achievement of the research objectives. This is done with adherence to Cresswell’s (2020) guidelines, in which open-ended interview questions were applied to get an authentic understanding of people’s experiences. Furthermore, through this interview approach, I encouraged my participants to fully and openly discuss their definition or meaning of the phenomenon being explored, which were the narratives of elementary school teachers regarding solid waste management. In light of the distinctive and authentic narratives of the participants, the interview has unraveled three (3) themes for the viewpoints of elementary school teachers about solid waste management. The first theme is the need for proper implementation of the policy. Even though the solid waste management program has been introduced for quite some time, everyone has not yet understood its importance. That may explain why it was not properly implemented in some schools. Teachers have shared that it would contribute greatly to maintaining a clean, healthy, and safe learning environment. The second theme pertains to the program’s contribution to nurturing good values. The solid waste management program was implemented in schools and communities to improve the order in sorting garbage and reduce the waste we produce. More than an act of caring for the environment, it also helps instill good values in the students. It hones them to become responsible and to develop care for their environment. The third theme was the importance of collective effort. Caring for our surroundings was not a one-man job. It requires collective effort. We live in the same environment and, more importantly, on the same planet. It was only proper that everyone contributes to maintaining its well-being. Meanwhile, the second research question tackles the coping mechanism teachers utilize to address the challenges of implementing a solid waste management program. There were two (2) emerging themes. The first theme emphasized the importance of students’ cooperation. In school, students

are not only there to learn or gain knowledge academically, but they are also taught essential life values like developing a sense of responsibility and care for the environment. Teachers have expressed that the program's implementation and success would be easily achieved through students' cooperation. The second theme of the research question was proper education on the policy. Students needed to understand the program's importance and purpose. Once they have reflected on it, they would further realize why the policy needs to be implemented. Finally, the third research question unfurled two (2) themes for the insights. The first insight is the importance of consistency in driving change. Teachers shared during the interview that for the program to be successful, there should be proper education, cooperation, and collective effort, which should be done consistently. This would make change possible. The second insight was about realizing that collaboration was essential. As mentioned, caring for the environment was never a one-man job; it requires a tremendous and collective effort from everyone in our community. In the school setting, every teacher and student should be in the same boat regarding implementing the policy so that there are noticeable environmental improvements. Based on the results of the thematic analysis of the responses from the participants of the study, the following findings and their corresponding themes were revealed: the viewpoints of elementary school teachers towards the implementation of solid waste management need proper implementation, nurturing good value, and collective effort. Meanwhile, the coping mechanisms of elementary school teachers were student cooperation and proper education on the policy. Lastly, the insights gained from the study's findings were that consistency drives change and collaboration is the key.

4.1. Implications—After thoroughly examining the data, I identified several significant key outcomes. These findings provide valuable insights and have notable implications for the analysis's subject. Solid waste management is critical to environmental sustainability and public health. Effective waste management involves collecting, transporting, disposing, and recycling or reusing waste materials to minimize their environmental impact. Municipalities worldwide face the challenge of dealing with increasing amounts of solid waste due to population growth, urbanization, and industrialization. One key component of solid waste management was waste reduction at the source through initiatives such as recycling, composting, and waste-to-energy programs. Recycling allows materials like paper, plastic, glass, and metal to be repurposed, reducing the demand for virgin resources and decreasing the amount of waste sent to landfills or incinerators. Composting organic waste, such as food scraps and yard trimmings, not only diverts waste from landfills but also produces nutrient-rich compost that can be used to enrich soil. On the educational landscape, solid waste management in schools is crucial for fostering environmental stewardship among students and staff, instilling sustainable habits from a young age. Schools generate significant waste daily, including paper, food scraps, and packaging materials. By implementing effective waste management practices, schools can reduce their environmental footprint, conserve resources, and teach students valuable lessons about waste reduction, recycling, and responsible consumption. Moreover, school solid waste management contributes to a healthier learning environment. Waste accumulation can attract pests, create unpleasant odors, and pose health risks to students and staff. Schools can maintain a clean and hygienic campus by ensuring regular waste collection, proper segregation, and disposal, minimizing the spread of diseases, and promoting student well-being. Teachers often recognize the importance of solid waste

management in schools as an opportunity to teach valuable lessons beyond the traditional curriculum. They understand that incorporating waste management practices into classroom activities and school-wide initiatives could promote environmental awareness, responsibility, and critical thinking among students. Teachers view solid waste management as a practical way to instill lifelong habits of sustainability and stewardship, empowering students to make positive contributions to their communities and the planet. Moreover, teachers appreciate the role of solid waste management in creating a conducive learning environment. They understand that a clean and hygienic school campus enhances student well-being and productivity. By implementing proper waste management strategies, teachers can minimize distractions caused by clutter and odors, creating a more focused and comfortable atmosphere for teaching and learning. Additionally, teachers recognize the educational value of integrating waste management into various subjects and extracurricular activities. They see opportunities to incorporate concepts of environmental science, mathematics, social studies, and even art and literature into lessons about waste reduction, recycling, and composting. Through hands-on experiences and real-world projects, teachers can engage students in meaningful learning experiences that foster critical thinking, problem-solving skills, and a sense of responsibility for the environment. Overall, teachers view solid waste management in schools as a holistic education approach that promotes academic learning and personal development. To sum up, solid waste management in schools was like planting seeds of sustainability in young minds, nurturing an eco-conscious garden. It was about keeping classrooms tidy and cultivating a culture of care for our planet. Schools sow the seeds of environmental stewardship by teaching students the art of waste reduction, recycling, and composting, ensuring a greener future bloom from

their efforts. Through hands-on activities and interdisciplinary learning, students tidy up their surroundings and grow into guardians of the Earth, equipped with the tools to nurture a thriving, sustainable world.

4.1.1. Future Directions—Based on the study's findings, the findings needed to be adequately relayed and used by the significant people for whom this research was intended. Educational leaders were more aware of the authentic first-hand narratives and the experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms employed by elementary school teachers through brand-new insights and perspectives regarding the implementation of solid waste management. Once they have recognized the challenges and reflected on them, they may implement programs or seminars targeting and focusing on improving policy implementation. They may spearhead policies to help realize solid waste management in different schools. The school heads were more informed and aware of the teachers' experiences with solid waste management. Based on the study's findings, they can also arrange information campaigns in schools to further educate the teachers and students on the importance of the program. The teachers. The study's findings can adequately inform the teachers about solid waste management and how it can be implemented inside the classroom. The findings can equip them to succeed in implementing the program. They may modify classroom rules and label trash cans appropriately to guide the students. Other stakeholders. They may provide support to enhance the program's implementation. The stakeholders may also be the source of other ways and means to solve some of the challenges faced by the teachers, such as additional trash cans, garbage bins, landfills, and spaces for trash that can be recycled. Future researchers may conduct the study, taking on the students' perspective on the implementation of solid waste management. It would be interesting to know their ways of making a change in

society through their little ways. It can also be helpful for other researchers to know perspectives because it would guide them in de-

5. References

- Adeolu, A. T., Enesi, D. O., & Adeolu, M. O. (2014). Assessment of secondary school students' knowledge, attitude and practice towards waste management in ibadan, oyo state, nigeria. *Journal of Research in Environmental Science and Toxicology*, 3(5), 66–73.
- Agut, M. P., Ull, M. A., & Minguet, P. A. (2013). Education for sustainable development in early childhood education in spain. evolution, trends and proposals. *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal*, 22(2), 213–228. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1350293x.2013.783299>
- Albert, A. O., & Olutayo, F. S. (2021). Cultural dimensions of environmental problems: A critical overview of solid waste generation and management in nigeria. *American International Journal of Multidisciplinary Scientific Research*, 8(1), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.46281/aijmsr.v8i1.1110>
- Al-Khatib, I. A., Monou, M., Abu Zahra, A. S., Shaheen, H. Q., & Kassinos, D. (2010). Solid waste characterization, quantification and management practices in developing countries. a case study: Nablus district – palestine. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 91(5), 1131–1138. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2010.01.003>
- Al-Naqbi, A. K., & Alshannag, Q. (2018). The status of education for sustainable development and sustainability knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors of uae university students. *International Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education*, 19(3), 566–588. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ijsh-06-2017-0091>
- Anderson, G. (2011). Students as valuable but vulnerable participants in research: Getting the balance right utilising a feminist approach and focus group interviews. *Evidence Based Midwifery*, 9(1), 30–34.
- Aspers, P. (2009). Empirical phenomenology: A qualitative research approach (the cologne seminars). *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3606033>
- Aspers, P., & Corte, U. (2019). What is qualitative in qualitative research. *Qualitative Sociology*, 42(2), 139–160. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11133-019-9413-7>
- Baawain, M., Al-Mamun, A., Omidvarborna, H., & Al-Amri, W. (2017). Ultimate composition analysis of municipal solid waste in muscat. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 148, 355–362.
- Bamberg, S., & Möser, G. (2007). Twenty years after hines, hungerford, and tomera: A new meta-analysis of psycho-social determinants of pro-environmental behaviour. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 27(1), 14–25.
- Barraza, L., Duque-Aristizabal, A. M., & Rebolledo, G. (2003). Environmental education from policy to practice. *Environmental Education Research*, 9(3), 347–357.
- Batara, O. (2022). Implementation of the solid waste management program in sta. maria, ilocos sur. *E-Dawa: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 1(1). <https://doi.org/10.56901/umem2605>

- Bedural, Z. L. (2018). Association between educational attainment and filipinos' values, attitudes and actions towards the environment. *Journal of Sustainable Development Education and Research*, 2(1), 59. <https://doi.org/10.17509/jsder.v2i1.12359>
- Beqiri, G. (2018, June). Rhetoric: How to inform, persuade, or motivate your audience [Retrieved from <https://virtualespeech.com/blog/rhetoric-inform-persuade-motivate-your-audience/>].
- Boateng, S., Boakye-Ansah, D., Baah, A., Aboagye, B., & Kyeremeh, P. A.-G. (2023). Solid waste management practices and challenges in rural and urban senior high schools in ashanti region, ghana. *Journal of Environmental and Public Health*, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2023/9694467>
- Borg, F., & Samuelsson, I. P. (2022). Preschool children's agency in education for sustainability: The case of sweden. *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal*, 30(1), 147–163. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1350293x.2022.2026439>
- Bourn, D., & Soysal, N. (2021). Transformative learning and pedagogical approaches in education for sustainable development: Are initial teacher education programmes in england and turkey ready for creating agents of change for sustainability? *Sustainability*, 13(16), 8973. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13168973>
- Bundhoo, Z. M. (2018). Solid waste management in least developed countries: Current status and challenges faced. *Journal of Material Cycles and Waste Management*, 20(3), 1867–1877. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10163-018-0728-3>
- Caulfield, J. (2019). How to do thematic analysis [Retrieved from <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/thematic-analysis/>].
- Chakraborti, D., Hussam, A., & Alauddin, M. (2003). Arsenic: Environmental and health aspects with special reference to groundwater in south asia. *Journal of Environmental Science and Health. Part A, Toxic/hazardous substances environmental engineering*, 38(1), xi–xv.
- Chatira-Muchopa, B., Tarisayi, K. S., & Chidarikire, M. (2019). Solid waste management practices in zimbabwe: A case study of one secondary school. *TD: The Journal for Transdisciplinary Research in Southern Africa*, 15(1), 1–5.
- Choi, H. J. (2016). *The environmental effectiveness of solid waste management* [Master's thesis].
- Coracero, E. E., Gallego, R. J., Frago, K. J., & Gonzales, R. J. (2021). A long-standing problem: A review on the solid waste management in the philippines. *Indonesian Journal of Social and Environmental Issues (IJSEI)*, 2(3), 213–220. <https://doi.org/10.47540/ijsei.v2i3.144>
- Creswell, J. W. (1998). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five traditions*. Sage Publications, Inc.
- Creswell, J. W. (2013). *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research*. PHI Learning Private Limited.
- Creswell, J. W. (2018). *Qualitative inquiry et research design: Choosing among five approaches*. SAGE.
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2023). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. SAGE Publications, Inc.
- Crotty, M. (2020). *The foundations of social research*. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003115700>
- Dalu, M. T., Cuthbert, R. N., Muhali, H., Chari, L. D., Manyani, A., Masunungure, C., & Dalu, T. (2020). Is awareness on plastic pollution being raised in schools? understanding perceptions of primary and secondary school educators. *Sustainability*, 12(17), 6775. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12176775>

- Davis, J. M., & Davis, J. E. (2020). Early childhood teacher education and education for sustainability. In *Researching early childhood education for sustainability* (pp. 111–124). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429446764-9>
- Dawadi, S. (2020). Thematic analysis approach: A step by step guide for elt research practitioners. *Journal of NELTA*, 25(1–2), 62–71. <https://doi.org/10.3126/nelta.v25i1-2.49731>
- Debrah, J. K., Vidal, D. G., & Dinis, M. A. (2021). Raising awareness on solid waste management through formal education for sustainability: A developing countries evidence review. *Recycling*, 6(1), 6. <https://doi.org/10.3390/recycling6010006>
- Dorn, C. (2020). «a new global ethic»: A history of the united nations international environmental education program, 1975-1995. *Foro de Educación*, 18(2), 83–108. <https://doi.org/10.14516/fde.808>
- Esmailizadeh, S., Shaghghi, A., & Taghipour, H. (2020). Key informants' perspectives on the challenges of municipal solid waste management in iran: A mixed method study. *Journal of Material Cycles and Waste Management*, 22, 1284–1298.
- Ferronato, N., & Torretta, V. (2019). Waste mismanagement in developing countries: A review of global issues. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 16(6), 1060. <https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/16/6/1060>
- Glaser, B. G., & Strauss, A. L. (2017). The discovery of grounded theory. In *The discovery of grounded theory* (pp. 1–18). <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203793206-1>
- Guba, E. G. (1981). Criteria for assessing the trustworthiness of naturalistic inquiries. *Educational Communication and Technology Journal*, 29(2), 75–91. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF0276677>
- Gugssa, M. A. (2023). Characterizing environmental education practices in ethiopian primary schools. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 102, 102848. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedudev.2023.102848>
- Gupta, V., Goel, S., & Rupa, T. G. (2019). Status of existing solid waste management initiatives in delhi schools. *International Journal of Advanced Research*, 7(10), 350–357. <https://doi.org/10.21474/ijar01/9837>
- Hammersley, M. (2013). Defining qualitative research. In *What is qualitative research?* <https://doi.org/10.5040/9781849666084.ch-001>
- Hennink, M., & Kaiser, B. N. (2022). Sample sizes for saturation in qualitative research: A systematic review of empirical tests. *Social Science Medicine*, 292, 114523. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2021.114523>
- Husamah, H., Suwono, H., Nur, H., & Dharmawan, A. (2022). Action competencies for sustainability and its implications to environmental education for prospective science teachers: A systematic literature review. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 18(8). <https://doi.org/10.29333/ejmste/12235>
- in Schools, S. W. M. (2016). Waste management in schools [Ecosan Services Foundation. Retrieved from <http://schools sanitation.com/pdf/Waste-Management-in-Schools.pdf>].
- Investopedia. (2023). Industrialization: What it is, examples, and its impact to society [Retrieved from <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/i/industrialization.asp>].
- Jafer, Y. J. (2019). Assessing kuwaiti pre-service science teachers' greenhouse effect perceptions and misconceptions. *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 18(4), 657–667. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10763-019-09992-1>

- Kimaryo, L. A. (2011). *Integrating environmental education in primary school education in tanzania: Teachers' perceptions and teaching practices* [Published Thesis, Åbo Akademi University]. Åbo Akademi University Press.
- Ko, A. C. C., & Lee, J. C. K. (2003). Teachers' perceptions of teaching environmental issues within the science curriculum: A hong kong perspective. *Journal of Science Education and Technology*, 12, 187–204.
- Lalamonan, E. N., & Comighud, S. M. (2020). Awareness and implementation of solid waste management (swm) practices. *IJRDO-Journal of Educational Research*, 5(5), 11–43. <http://13.234.104.160/index.php/er/article/download/3694/2777>
- Laroche, M., Bergeron, J., & Barbaro-Forleo, G. (2001). Targeting consumers who are willing to pay more for environmentally friendly products. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 18(6), 503–520.
- Leicht, A., Heiss, J., & Byun, W. J. (2018). Issues and trends in education for sustainable development. UNESCO Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.54675/yelo2332>
- Lualhati, G. P. (2019). Environmental awareness and participation of filipino pre-service teachers. *JPBI (Jurnal Pendidikan Biologi Indonesia)*, 5(2), 345–352. <https://doi.org/10.22219/jpbi.v5i2.8524>
- Marello, M., & Helwege, A. (2018). Solid waste management and social inclusion of wastepickers: Opportunities and challenges. *Latin American Perspectives*, 45(1), 108–129. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0094582x17726083>
- Marpa, E. (2020). Navigating environmental education practices to promote environmental awareness and education. *International Journal on Studies in Education*, 2(1), 45–57. <https://doi.org/10.46328/ijonse.8>
- Marshall, M. N. (1996). Sampling for qualitative research. *Family Practice*, 13, 522–525. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/fampra/13.6.522>
- Marshall, R., & Farahbakhsh, K. (2013). Systems approaches to integrated solid waste management in developing countries. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2012.12.023>
- Matunog, V., & Awa, A. (2013). Solid waste generation rate in ozamiz city, philippines. *Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 1(1), 73–92. <https://doi.org/10.7828/jmds.v2i1.396>
- McIntosh, K., Predy, L. K., Upreti, G., Hume, A. E., Turri, M. G., & Mathews, S. (2013). Perceptions of contextual features related to implementation and sustainability of school-wide positive behavior support. *Journal of Positive Behavior Interventions*, 16(1), 31–43. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1098300712470723>
- Mkhonto, B., & Mnguni, L. (2021). The impact of a rural school-based solid waste management project on learners' perceptions, attitudes and understanding of recycling. *Recycling*, 6(4), 71.
- Molina, R. A., & Catan, I. (2021). Solid waste management awareness and practices among senior high school students in a state college in zamboanga city, philippines. *Aquademia*, 5(1), ep21001. <https://doi.org/10.21601/aquademia/9579>
- Morrow, R., Rodriguez, A., & King, N. (2021). Paul colaizzi's descriptive phenomenological methodology. In *Introduction to phenomenology: Focus on methodology* (pp. 19–30). <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781071909669.n8>
- Morse, J. M. (1994). Designing funded qualitative research. In N. K. Denzin & Y. S. Lincoln (Eds.), *Handbook of qualitative research* (2nd). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

- Mullet, D. R. (2018). A general critical discourse analysis framework for educational research. *Journal of Advanced Academics*, 29(2), 116–142. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1932202x18758260>
- Naeem, S. (2019). Internal validity in research. helping research writing for student and professional researchers [Retrieved from <http://researcharticles.com/index.php/internal-validity-research/>].
- Nathanson, J. (2019). Solid waste management [Retrieved from <https://www.britannica.com/technology/solid-waste-management>].
- Neubauer, B. E., Witkop, C. T., & Varpio, L. (2019). How phenomenology can help us learn from the experiences of others. *Perspectives on Medical Education*, 8(2), 90–97. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40037-019-0509-2>
- Nolasco, M., Beguia, Y., & Padua, M. (2019). Solid waste management in naga city: Its culture of information dissemination [Retrieved from <http://www.apjmr.com/APJMR-2019.7.04.02>]. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 7(4), 12–17.
- Olsen, S. K., Miller, B. G., Eitel, K. B., & Cohn, T. C. (2020). Assessing teachers' environmental citizenship based on an adventure learning workshop: A case study from a social-ecological systems perspective. *Journal of Science Teacher Education*, 31(8), 869–893. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1046560x.2020.1771039>
- Ortega-Dela Cruz, R. A., & Nabor Jr., A. P. (2022). Pupils' awareness, knowledge, attitude, and practice of school-based solid waste management in a public elementary school in the philippines. *University of Wah Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(1), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.56220/uwjss2022/0501/01>
- Panko, M., & Sharma, R. (2016). Integrating waste management and pollution control in tertiary vocational education programmes: Case studies. *International Journal of Information and Education Technology*, 6(3), 228–231. <https://doi.org/10.7763/ijiet.2016.v6.690>
- Panzo, T. I., Góis, J. C., & Mendes, J. M. (2022). Environmental awareness on solid waste management practices: A case study in angolan secondary schools. *Journal of Civil Engineering and Environmental Sciences*, 8(2), 76–81.
- Patton, M. Q. (2002). *Qualitative research & evaluation methods* (3rd). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Periathamby, A. (2011). Municipal waste management. In *Waste* (pp. 109–125). Academic Press.
- Pöldnrnk, J. (2015). Optimisation of the economic, environmental and administrative efficiency of the municipal waste management model in rural areas. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 97, 55–65.
- Pramling Samuelsson, I. (2011). Why we should begin early with esd: The role of early childhood education. *International Journal of Early Childhood*, 43(2), 103–118. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13158-011-0034-x>
- Prisco, A. A., & Cubillas, A. U. (2022). Ecological solid waste management program of elementary schools in agusan del norte division: Success stories, challenges and prospects.
- Programme, U. N. E., & Association, I. S. W. (2015). Integrated solid waste management framework. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0734242X211035926>
- Punongbayan, C. M., Abu, S. P., Arago, M. P., Caponpon, M. G., Marie, A., Geron, C., & Manzano, A. (2014). Waste management practices of an educational institution. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education, Arts and Sciences*, 1(4), 15–20.

- Puri, K., Joshi, R., & Singh, V. (2020). Open garbage dumps near protected areas in uttarakhand: An emerging threat to asian elephants in the shivalik elephant reserve. *Journal of Threatened Taxa*, 12(11), 16571–16575. <https://doi.org/10.11609/jott.4392.12.11.16571-16575>
- R. Cruzada Jr., D., & Benedictos, E. (2022). A gender perspective on solid waste management practices: A climate change mitigation initiative. *International Journal of Advanced Research*, 10(04), 463–474. <https://doi.org/10.21474/ijar01/14569>
- Resnik, D. (2020). What is ethics in research and why is it important? [National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences. Retrieved from <https://www.niehs.nih.gov/research/resources/bioethics/whatis/index.cfm>].
- Reyes, M. J., & Madrigal, D. V. (2020). Assessing students' awareness, attitude, and practices on solid waste management in a philippine catholic school. *Philippine Social Science Journal*, 3(1), 9–20. <https://doi.org/10.52006/main.v3i1.125>
- Romero, P. (2020). Phl facing garbage crisis: 16.6m metric tons of waste this year can fill 99 philippine arenas [The Philippine Star. Retrieved from <https://www.onenews.ph/phl-facing-garbage-crisis-16-6-million-metric-tons-of-waste-this-year-can-fill-99-philippine-arenas>].
- San Juan, F. (2019). Community participation in solid waste management program of selected community associations in zamboanga city, philippines. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 7(4), 42–49. <http://www.apjmr.com/APJMR-2019.7.04.06>
- Saracini, A., & Sidorenko, S. (2019). Application of creative thinking method in solving urban environment waste management as a social problem. *South East European Journal of Architecture and Design*, 2019, 102. <https://doi.org/10.3889/seejad.2019.10043>
- Sarino, M. (2014). Proper waste disposal makes for disaster-free communities [Article, Manila Bulletin. Retrieved from <http://www.mb.com.ph/proper-waste-disposal-makesfor-disaster-free-communities/>].
- Sharholly, M., Ahmad, K., Mahmood, G., & Trivedi, R. C. (2008). Municipal solid waste management in indian cities. a review. *Journal of Waste Management*, 28, 459–467.
- Soni, A., Das, P. K., Hashmi, A. W., Yusuf, M., Kamyab, H., & Chelliapan, S. (2022). Challenges and opportunities of utilizing municipal solid waste as alternative building materials for sustainable development goals: A review. *Sustainable Chemistry and Pharmacy*, 27, 100706. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scp.2022.100706>
- Subedi, K. R. (2021). Determining the sample in qualitative research. *Scholars' Journal*, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.3126/scholars.v4i1.42457>
- Summers, M., Corney, G., & Childs, A. (2003). Teaching sustainable development in primary schools: An empirical study of issues for teachers. *Environmental Education Research*, 9(3), 327–346.
- UNESCO-UNEP. (1994). Population: Working for an equitable, sustainable development in harmony with the environment [Connect. 19(4): pp. 1-2].
- URT. (2009). National education and environment communication strategy (2nd).
- Van Niekerk, I. M. (2014). *Waste management behaviour: A case study of school children in mpumalanga, south africa* [Doctoral dissertation].
- Van Petegem, P., Blicck, A., & Van Ongevalle, J. (2007). Conceptions and awareness concerning environmental education: A zimbabwean case-study in three secondary teacher education colleges. *Environmental Education Research*, 13(3), 287–306.

- Vasileiou, K., Barnett, J., Thorpe, S., & Young, T. (2018). Characterising and justifying sample size sufficiency in interview-based studies: Systematic analysis of qualitative health research over a 15-year period. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, 18(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-018-0594-7>
- Villanueva, R. (2013a). Proper solid waste management: Education, engineering, enterprise and enforcement [Article. The Philippine Star. Retrieved from <http://www.philstar.com/science-and-technology/2013/01/03/892576/proper-solid-waste-management-education-engineering>].
- Villanueva, R. (2013b). Proper solid waste management: Education, engineering, enterprise and enforcement [Retrieved from <https://www.philstar.com/business/science-and-environment/2013/01/03/892576/proper-solid-waste-management-education-engineeringenterprise-and-enforcement>].
- Wellington, J. (2015). Educational research. <https://doi.org/10.5040/9781474236966>
- Wirihana, L., Welch, A., Williamson, M., Christensen, M., Bakon, S., & Craft, J. (2018). Using Colaizzi's method of data analysis to explore the experiences of nurse academics teaching on satellite campuses. *Nurse Researcher*, 25(4), 30–34. <https://doi.org/10.7748/nr.2018.e1516>
- WWF-Philippines. (2018). The scourge of single – use plastic in the philippines [Retrieved from https://wwf.panda.org/knowledge_hub/where_we_work/coraltriangle/?329831/The-scourge-ofsingle-use-plastic-in-the-Philippines].
- Žukauskas, P., Vveinhardt, J., & Andriukaitienė, R. (2018). Research ethics. In *Management culture and corporate social responsibility*. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.70629>